

8-Theory and the Lagrangian Variation

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Abstract:

The following is an analysis of Lagrangian $\mathcal{L} = T - V$ function variation on the new theoretical framework of the 8-Theory. The main subject of the paper is the appropriate transition of the terms of the Lagrangian to a varying Lorentz manifold, which is an Einstein manifold (M, g_E) with signature $(3,1)$. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary $M = M_0 \times R$.

Introduction

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad - \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\mathcal{L} = T - V \quad (1.11)$$

How can a representation of the Lagrangian be made on the varying Lorentz manifold, is the main question one will analyze in this short essay. Of course, the real answer to that question is one does not know. However, educated guess will be made. The kinetic term could be associated to the outward matric expansion, due to $(\partial g / \partial t)$ term, which is synonymous with energy in physical theories.

$$\left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \right) = \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial t} \right) = \frac{\partial^2 E'}{\partial t^2} \quad (1.12)$$

That is the kinetic term. A Ricci Tensor overtime, yielding an energy expansion outward causing a matric acceleration on the object generating the energy. That is the main equation that was derived by putting an Einstein manifold in Euler Lagrange Equation. Now, what is the potential energy in the 8T framework? In physical theories, the potential is associated with the mass, which is certain feature of the object itself. In the 8T we do not have any objects, the objects are manifestations of discretizing and partitioning the term $\delta g \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^K \delta g_i = 0$ in equation (1.) to vanish into fermions. How can we translate that into a potential term?

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

Since we would like to measure how much arbitrary variations the object we measure contain, and those arbitrary variations are two and three divisible to vanish into matter, two distinct elements which created threefold combinations, to get a measure of the amount of arbitrary variations, the action needed is the following Transformation:

$$\sum_{i=1}^K \delta g_i = 0 \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^K |\delta g_i| = \mathcal{V}_{8T} \quad (1.21)$$

The idea, whether correct or not, was to take the absolute number of varying elements participating in the construction of the object. The operation was done via the insight we gained in previous paper, two distinct elements which differ in sign, so by eliminating the minus sign we can estimate how many arbitrary variations appear in the cluster. To sum up, the current variation of the Lagrangian that may vary overtime with understanding the latitude of the 8T better is:

$$\mathcal{L} = \left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \right) - \sum_{i=1}^K |\delta g_i| \quad (2)$$

The energy, causing outward acceleration minus the total amount of arbitrary variations constructed in the cluster.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)